

The Application of Credit Score Assessment System (SIPAK) in Accelerating Functional Promotions: An Effort to Realize SDGs in Politeknik Negeri Bandung

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ABSTRACT : *This study aims to analyze the acceleration program for the promotion of functional positions of lecturers in Politeknik Negeri Bandung (Polban) and its correlation to the realization of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in education. The method used was qualitative in which researchers seek to explore in-depth data about existing phenomena and then analyze them using the nine aspects of human resource capacity development. The primary data sources were obtained from interviews and secondary data sources were obtained from journals, literature studies, online news, and newspapers related to the promotion of functional positions of lecturers. The results show that Polban has implemented an acceleration program for functional position promotion of lectures through SIPAK systems with good results and the number of lecturers who promote the functional position has increased. This study concludes that by referring to the nine aspects of human resource capacity development, the acceleration program for functional position promotion of lecturers can be more effective and efficient and can achieve the set goals.*

KEYWORDS -Effective and efficient, functional, capacity development

I. INTRODUCTION

The Sustainable Development Goals or SDGs are a universal program that was initiated by the United Nations (UN) to protect the earth, to end poverty in the world permanently, and to ensure that by 2030 all mankind will enjoy peace and prosperity by maintaining a balance between the three dimensions of sustainable development, namely environmental, social, and economic [1]. These SDGs have the same goals as the National Medium-Term Development Plan (Rencana Pembangunan Jangka Menengah Nasional /RPJMN) 2020-2024 of the Indonesian state, i.e. to improve people's welfare. Therefore, the SDGs as a global development agenda is in line with the RPJMN and are an inseparable part of the national development agenda [2]. The SDGs are an agreement of 193 member states of the United Nations which have 17 main goals, where the 4th goal (SDG-4) is quality education for all. The goal in the field of education must be achieved by maximizing various efforts that can encourage Indonesia to become a country that plays an active role in realizing these SDGs. The SDG-4 covers various aspects of education, including participation, quality and learning outcomes, school infrastructure, quality of teachers/lecturers, safety and hygiene in schools, and commitment to global citizenship values in education [3].

Politeknik Negeri Bandung (Polban) is one of the higher education institutions that participate in the implementation of SDGs in education where one of the programs is to increase lecturers' capacity. Lecturers are professional educators and scientists with the main task of transforming, developing, and disseminating science, technology, and art through education, research, and community services. In carrying out these tasks, competence is required. Competence is a set of knowledge, skills, and behaviors that must be possessed, internalized, and controlled by lecturers in carrying out their professional duties [4].

If the goal to be achieved by Polban is to produce qualified lecturers, then capacity building for the lecturers is required. The lecturer capacity development is carried out by Polban management through initiating an acceleration program for functional position promotions using the Credit Score Assessment System (SIPAK) where this program was firstly initiated and compiled in 2020. Viewed from the aspect of human resource capacity development, to achieve the development goals effectively and efficiently, the process taken in this development needs to be focused on the following aspects: 1) Performance capacity, 2) Personal capacity, 3) Workloads, 4) Supervisory capacity, 5) Facility capacity, 6) Support service capacity, 7) Systems capacity, 8) Structural capacity, and 9) Role capacity [5]. These nine aspects are used as the basis for accelerating the promotion of the functional position of lecturers in Polban. When all these nine aspects have been fulfilled through these acceleration program, it can be ascertained that Polban has qualified lecturer resources that are ready to develop their respective careers and produce the best graduates. One measurement of the higher education quality is seen from the quality of its human resources (lecturers), while the quality of lecturers can be proven by the level of education and functional positions [6]. If a lecturer has a high functional position, then it shows that the lecturer has fulfilled the three elements in the Tridharma of Higher Education which includes education and teaching, research, and community service with a high legal value. A high functional position will also encourage the career advancement of a lecturer. For a lecturer, a career is a reflection of success in their field because it is a reflection of the responsibilities, desires, interests, and skills of each individual so that a lecturer's career is a series or sequence of job positions held during being a lecturer. Career development can show how a lecturer performs in his institution [7]. In addition to providing attitudes or skills to lecturers, universities must also work to improve the quality of lecturer competencies to be able to know the level of knowledge, expertise, and attitude of lecturers who are believed to be able to influence lecturer performance [8].

However, the number of lecturers who propose a functional position promotion in Polban is still relatively small. Until April 2021, the functional position of lecturers who still hold on to the same position shows a fairly large number as shown in the following table:

Table 1 Functional Position of Polban's Lecturer

Position	More than 10 years	Less than 10 years
Asisten Ahli (Assistant Professor)	38	45
Lektor (Assistant Professor)	115	51
Lektor Kepala (Associate Professor)	77	100
Total	230	196

Source: Personnel Department, 2021

Table 1 presents as many as 426 lecturers out of a total of 504 lecturers who are in a stagnant position in their functional positions for a long period, which is approximately 10 years. This shows that the motivation to realize the SDGs in the field of education is facing a fairly severe challenge where this condition arises from Polban's internal environment. The perception that lecturers are now in a safe and comfortable position causes them to think that it is not a matter if they do not promote their functional position. This perception also makes the lecturers in Polban are reluctant to promote their functional position and not interested in having a better career.

Several factors cause lecturers reluctant to promote their functional position. Research conducted by [6] shows that insight into functional positions, leadership support, teaching load, and ease of procedures are factors that hamper lecturers from carrying out functional promotions. In addition, [9] stated that procedures, support, and workload are dominant factors that affect the difficulty of lecturers to promote a functional position. One of the obstacles to increasing the capacity of lecturers is the lecturer's lack of interest in conducting research which results in the inhibition of the lecturer's career advancement [10]. The research results from [8] stated that if management provides clarity on the career path of lecturers, then they will hasten to improve their competence which will immediately improve their performance. Meanwhile [11] stated that providing training to lecturers will develop the lecturers' capacity. The state of the art of this research is the use of the nine aspects of human resource capacity development so that the research results will be more effective and efficient, on target, and support the achievement of the set goals.

Based on this description, the researchers focusing this research on the analysis of the acceleration program for functional position promotions using the SIPAK system that carried out by Polban management to increase the lecturers' capacity as part of the realization of the SDGs, especially in the field of education. Moreover, this research emphasizes the nine aspects of developing human resource capacity in its implementation according to Potter & Brough as seen in the image below.

Fig. 1 data processed by researchers, 2021

II. RESEARCH METHOD

The research method used was qualitative which aims to understand existing phenomena based on qualitative data such as words, language, actions, motivation, and perceptions [12]. The primary data source used was obtained from the results of open interviews with purposively selected informants who understand the process of functional positions promotion or SIPAK system in Polban. They are Polban management represented by the Deputy Director of Academic Affairs, the head of Personnel Department, and lecturer representatives. In addition, the researchers also used secondary data sources in the form of reports on the identity of the lecturers and the functional position of each lecturer which were obtained from the Report on the Performance of Polban. Moreover, the secondary data sources were also collected from literature studies, either article in journals, annual reports, online data sources, and newspapers [13].

Analysis of research data followed the rules that combine literature insight with the scientific insight of the researcher. As it is known, qualitative studies put the researcher as a research instrument [13].

The data were analyzed using the nine aspects in the human resource capacity development proposed by Potter and Brough. To make this analysis valid and accurate, data triangulation was carried out so that the correct interpretation was obtained from the results of the data analysis.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In achieving the 4th SDGs target related to education, the biggest challenge faced is how to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education [3]. Universities will be able to produce quality graduates if the lecturers who teach have good quality as well. The term quality cannot be separated from the term competence, where a lecturer is required to have a holistic or comprehensive competence that will show his capacity as a lecturer. In general, it can be said that human resource capacity is the competence of individuals within an institution to carry out their duties, functions, and authorities in achieving goals effectively and efficiently [14]. The idea of human resources development aims to increase the capacity of individuals/lecturers in carrying out their responsibilities professionally and improve their technical abilities [15].

Polban as one of the higher education institutions that seek to participate in realizing the goals of the SDGs has a program to accelerate functional position promotions or SIPAK system to describe policies that have been prepared relating to the development of human resource capacity. In general, the rules regarding the promotion of functional positions are directed at encouraging the function of lecturers to be more optimal, showing an increasingly measurable and quality performance, and referring to international lecturer competitions [6]. The policy of human resource capacity development made by Polban aims to focus more on strengthening institutions where this is necessary to be able to compete with other universities in producing quality graduates. Human resources capacity development programs need to be designed by applying a method that can change the human resources knowledge, skills, expertise, attitudes, and behavior. This program needs to be made so that individual capacity development can contribute a positive impact on capacity building, institutional strengthening, and system strengthening [16]. The development of lecturer resource capacity in Polban is implemented using the nine aspects of human resource development from Potter & Brough.

3.1 Performance and Facility Capacity

Performance Capacity refers to the availability of all facilities and infrastructure that support the implementation of a job [17]. Based on interview with Deputy Director of Academic Affairs, Polban management in implementing this functional promotion acceleration program has prepared all the facilities and infrastructure needed to support the implementation of this acceleration program properly. Polban has created SIPAK information systems that facilitate the lecturers to input their data. Then, Polban has prepared reviewers in each department to help the lecturers assessed their scientific work. At the central level, Polban management also has created a team of verifiers who will verify the data in SIPAK. The essence of this performance capacity is how to make Polban management provides all the tools that function as a support for a performance [16]. SIPAK is the new thing for Polban lecturers because Polban management has only initiated this system since the end of 2020. According to this, some lecturers answered that they still do not understand how to run this application system. To make all the lecturers understand to use the system, Polban management conducted a socialization program and training on the use of SIPAK once in a month and it repeated. This is in line with the core of Facility Capacity; management ensures that for every launch of a new information system, management will provide facilities that will be used as a training ground for lecturers who are also equipped with instructors who are experts in the field [17].

3.2 Personal and Support Service Capacity

One of the lecturers' obligations is to carry out career development in the form of a functional position promotion [18]. It is mandatory because lecturers are the main resource that makes the biggest contribution to

universities to produce the best graduates who will improve the institutional function of Polban as an actor in SDGs implementation in the field of education. However, in reality, based on collected data given by Personnel Department there are still 426 lecturers in Polban who have not carried out these obligations regularly and there are even 230 lecturers who have not made functional promotions for more than 10 years. This shows that there is an understanding that has not been conveyed to Polban lecturers about the importance of functional promotions so that they can pursue a better career [18]. In contrast to the research from [19], lecturer delays in managing functional promotions are influenced by two factors, namely the personal factor and the unsupportive administrative system factor. Personal capacity is a condition where a lecturer has sufficient knowledge about functional promotion and all implementation procedures, skill and confidence to properly manage functional promotions, and attending training both managerial skills training and self-motivation training [17]. Individual motivational drivers of career progression are not constant over the course of a career; these are most commonly linked to past, current and predicted future career experiences [20]. Individuals might have different motivations to invest in different academic roles that conflict with each other in terms of time and resources; such as teaching versus research, reflecting the ever-present conflict between these roles [21]. Every human being has a different motivation when doing something and this motivation has a considerable influence on the desire to be able to further increase his capacity so that the capacity of a lecturer can show his qualification to carry out his functional promotion. Personal capacity is important to be considered because it can be used as the basis for preparing human resource capacity development programs [16]. Management support is necessary for developing this personal capacity. Support from management can be in the form of providing training facilities [16]. Based on interview with Polban Management, the result obtained that during the pandemic era of COVID19, training for lecturers is accessible as it can be carried out online so there is no reason for lecturers not to take part in training regarding this SIPAK system. The support provided by Polban management is not only limited to providing training but support in the form of personal and group consultations is also given to lecturers. Through the WhatsApp Group platform in which intensive communication and discussion is carried out with topics related to functional promotions so that Polban management can deliver all matters related to functional promotions through the platform to all Polban lecturers.

3.3 Workload Capacity

Based on the interview's result with lecturer representatives, it reveals several reasons are put forward by the lecturers regarding their reluctance to increase their functional positions. One of them is because of their workload. Workload capacity is closely related to individual workloads [5]. When a lecturer has a large workload in the sense that the lecturer holds many classes and teaches several courses at once, then they seem to run out of energy and time to prepare their functional position promotions. This is of course a concern for Polban management to map the portion of each lecturer in teaching so that the work overload can be minimized or even prevented. In addition to teaching, lecturers are also required to fulfill all the elements of the Tridharma of Higher Education; education and teaching, research, and community service. The Tridharma of Higher Education is a mandatory task of the lecturers. The teaching load and other tasks given by the institution become factors that must be faced in applying for functional positions. So the lecturers must be able to divide the time as best as possible to organize these tasks. This means that lecturers' habits and adjustability are required so that they are willing and able to follow the functional promotion as it is to improve their career [6].

To overcome the lecturers' workload, it is essential to have a special party to supervise this condition [17]. So far, Polban has a special team that handles the workload of lecturers, where this team is responsible for reviewing the completeness of the workload files and checking the suitability between reports made by lecturers and supporting evidence. This supports the management and the lecturer because it facilitates early screening when there are findings that must be immediately corrected by the lecturers. In addition to the elements of education and teaching, lecturers also must conduct research and community services. The element of research often becomes the cause of lecturers being reluctant to promote the functional position. This happens because some lecturers have a belief that they cannot conduct research independently. Seeing the phenomenon that the element of research is one of the biggest obstacles for lecturers to carry out functional promotions, Polban management conducts various efforts to increase the lecturers' interest in researching various training in writing

scientific papers. To increase the interest of lecturers in writing scientific papers, solid cooperation between policymakers is needed so that the steps taken by the management can increase the capacity of lecturers in research. On the other hand, support from institutions in the form of capacity building is needed for individuals, groups, and organizations in implementing research. The capacity building of lecturers who conduct research should pay attention to the following points: 1. Capacity building is a continuous process, 2. Strengthening ongoing processes, 3. Involving all relevant stakeholders, 4. Involving support and the role of external experts, 5. The ability/core competence of the researcher must be evaluated from the beginning to find out if there are gaps that must be addressed immediately. The required capabilities and resources are evaluated regularly, 6. Involvement of all managers and leaders, as well as organizational development, is needed, 7. Development of expertise groups [10].

3.4 System and Supervisory Capacity

System capacity is closely related to a work unit system consisting of several components (information traffic, managerial processes, and decision making) or different elements but supporting the same goal [16]. Based on the interview with the Deputy Director of Academic Affairs, the result obtained that the program for accelerating functional promotions in Polban has been started in early 2020. Before 2020, the procedures used to apply for functional promotions were still conducted manually but in 2020 Polban management through the Deputy Director of the Academic Affairs has created a system related to functional promotions named the Credit Score Assessment System (Sistem Informasi Penilaian Angka Kredit-SIPAK). This system is integrated work units and are interrelated with one another. SIPAK answers the obstacles faced by lecturers who want to assess their scientific works. Previously, lecturers assessed their scientific works manually by contacting reviewers. This is considered an obstacle because lecturers often cannot meet directly with the reviewers so that the process of evaluating scientific papers is hampered. In addition, the condition of the Covid-19 pandemic where most of the activities are carried out at home or work from home, SIPAK facilitates lecturers to be able to assess their scientific works online by only uploading their scientific papers. The system will automatically link the lecturer's scientific work submissions with related parties such as the Head of the Department and the reviewers. The results of the assessment of the scientific paper will be accepted by the lecturers in a relatively short time.

Further more SIPAK is a system created to assist lecturers who wants to apply for a functional promotion to carry out all the application processes through the online system. In SIPAK, various menus help the lecturers to complete and upload all the requirements, starting from the lecturer's identity, credit numbers to uploading all the necessary administrative documents. The role of the information system in the process of applying for functional positions is currently beneficial for lecturers in facilitating the process of applying for functional positions and also the team of the reviewer in checking documents [6].

The result of the processing data indicate that there is an acceleration of functional promotions since SIPAK system is used. These following figure shows a comparison between the acceleration of functional promotion before and after the use of the SIPAK system.

Fig. 2 The Acceleration of Functional Position Promotion before SIPAK system

The figure above shows a graph of functional promotions in the last ten years before SIPAK system is used and it indicates a slow movement. From the previous discussion it is understood that there are several factors inhibiting the promotion of functional position such as complicated procedure for submitting functional promotions manually.

Fig. 3 The Acceleration of Functional Position Promotion after SIPAK system

The figure above shows the increasing of lecturers who have promoted their functional positions promotion because the SIPAK system make them easier to do their functional positions promotion. This condition bring Polban become the university that have a good capacity supported by the capacity of lecturers.

Although SIPAK system can be a solution to the obstacles faced by lecturers, it is undeniable that this system still have weaknesses. This can be seen from the results of interviews with lecturer representatives, it is revealed that when filling in data on the SIPAK systems, the system often experiences "system errors" or there are work orders that have not been understood by the lecturer so that data entry cannot be finalized immediately. In the other words, this system can facilitate the process of data input, but they can be a technical obstacle during the process of finalizing the data submission because lecturers do not understand the instructions or procedures for filling out this system. In the previous discussion, it is mentioned that management provides training for using

the SIPAK application system. Welcoming the era of society 5.0, it is hoped that all lecturers are able and accustomed to working using information technology systems. Although there will always be obstacles from this IT system and humans are expected not to rely too much on information technology because the spirit of strengthening human resource capacity is through the truly humanist activities, so that it makes humans skillful in using technology but not become robots [16].

Practically, the SIPAK application systems must always be supervised by the management. This is in line with the aspect of supervisory capacity where this aspect focuses on supervision carried out by the competent authorities. This system can manipulate data because of their manless nature so that everything is done based on work orders from operators. Thus, it is required for reporting and monitoring the performance of this system to realize the accountability of the information produced [17].

3.5 Role and Structural Capacity

Role capacity is closely related to the role of a person or individual in an organization while structural capacity is related to the existence of a forum in which cross-sectoral discussions occur to make the right and accurate decisions [16]). SIPAK system is initiated by an authorized official who will make a very important decision for the continuation of the career of the lecturer who proposes a functional promotion. An important role is required from a leader and in Polban its representatives by the Deputy Director of Academic Affairs, so that the decisions taken are correct and fulfill all elements fairly for the lecturers. Leaders are not allowed to commit fraud in terms of making decisions to determine whether a lecturer is worthy to be promoted to his functional position. A leader who hopes to achieve maximum performance in an organization must pay attention to factors that affect the performance of its employees, one of which is career development [22]. Although the final decision regarding the graduation of lecturer status is in the hands of the competent authority, the rules must still be followed where the decision-maker must wait for information from the officials below him who are also involved in assessing the credit score of the lecturer such as reviewers, heads of departments, verifiers, and the personnel department who have complete records regarding the identity of the lecturer. If it is implemented, then the results of the decisions taken will be final because it carries the principle of fairness.

IV. CONCLUSION

The program for accelerating the promotion of lecturer functional positions in Polban by creating the SIPAK system is going well and succeeded to help lecturers reaching their new functional positions. It can be seen from a great number of lecturer do the promotion of their functional positions, and this data will always be increasing because this acceleration program is still running until now. This shows the success of the program initiated by Polban management, which in this case is represented by the Deputy Director of Academic Affairs and their staff. The success of this functional promotion acceleration program is because of its implementation referring to the nine aspects contained in the development of human resource capacity. Each aspect describes the real conditions performed by Polban management in carrying out the program to accelerate the promotion of the functional position of Polban lecturers. When individual capacity increases it also increases organizational capacity because by the acceleration of functional position promotion, there will be a great number of professor and associate professor in Polban. This can be proven by the increasing of institutional accreditation which placed Polban into one of the universities with a large applicants. This condition is closely related to the objectives of the SDGs in the field of education, which is to improve the quality of lecturers through increasing the capacity of lecturers. With this effort, Polban can play an active role in producing the best graduates and compete with others universities. However, there are several obstacles in its implementation so that researchers need to provide input. First, Polban management should increase the capacity of the technology system used in the SIPAK applications so that it will minimize the occurrence of "system errors" because it will hamper the process of submitting the requirements. Second, Polban management should held the comparative study to another universities in order to get more knowledge about the promotion of lecturer functional positions. Third, for another researcher should continue and develop this research's topic using another theory.

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